

INK PRODUCTION WITH NATURAL SINOP CLAY PIGMENT AND EXAMINATION PRINTABILITY PROPERTIES OF ECO-FRIENDLY INK

Dogan Tutak¹, Arif Ozcan¹, Emine Arman Kandirmaz¹, Serat Kotan²

¹Marmara University, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Printing Technologies
Department, Turkey

²Sinop University, Gerze Vocational School Audio-Audious Techniques and
Media Production Department, Turkey

Original scientific paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10008231
dtutak@marmara.edu.tr

Abstract: *Sinop clay is found in large quantities in the province of Sinop in the Black Sea region of Turkey and takes its name from this city. Sinop clay is abundant in this region. Due to its easy use and low cost, Sinop clay can be suitable for use in new and different industrial applications. Sinop clay, which was used in many fields before, was also used as an alternative pigment for lithography printing inks. In the study, lithography ink was prepared by using 20% and 25% pigment from the pigment prepared using Sinop clay. The prepared ink was printed on coated paper with the IGT C1 test printer. ΔE values were calculated by measuring the CIEL*a*b* values of the printed papers and comparing them with the Pantone catalogue. At the same time, the print gloss and rub resistance tests of the printed papers were carried out. The results were very close to the Pantone® 7527 C. ΔE difference between the two colors is 2.31. This shows that the difference is so close that it cannot be seen with the naked eye.*

Keywords: printing ink, pigment, pantone

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the seriousness of environmental problems, environmentalism has ceased to be a matter of choice and has become a basic condition that must be applied for the survival of humanity (Abd El-Gawad et al.,

2022). With the development of the economy, environmental protection and health have aroused great concern all over the world (Liu et al., 2018). As a result, more environmentally friendly, natural, and sustainable products have been turned.

All printing inks consist of four main components: colorants, binders, solvents, and additives. The properties of components change due to the printing process and the printing substrates that come into contact with the ink (Özcan, 2007; Sabin et al., 1997). Lithography printing processes require paste inks. Conventional printing inks used in these applications are usually created with the following formulation. A hydrocarbon and/or alkyd resin; a hydrocarbon solvent; a pigment; and optional additives. For example, a typical lithography ink composition is defined as 15-25% hydrocarbon or alkyd resins as a vehicle, 50-70% mineral oil solvent and 15-20% pigment as colorant (Erhan et al., 1995).

The interest in pigments is increasing day by day both in scientific and practical applications. It is one of the main components of coating and ink manufacturers, which represents a very important sector in the industry due to its wide application areas (Abd El-Gawad et al., 2022.; Ozcan & Tutak, 2021). Pigment is the substance that gives an object its color. The perception of each pigment in different colors is entirely due to the chemical structure of that pigment and the bonds that make it up (Aydemir et al., 2018). In order to obtain sufficient color power on the substrate, lithography inks must be homogeneous and more pigmented compared to other inks (Hayta et al., 2022).

Natural pigments can be obtained directly from plants and microorganisms or can be found directly in nature. Natural pigment is not only harmless to the body, but also some pigments are beneficial to health due to trace elements. Environmentally friendly products have become the indispensable theme of today's technologies. However, the printing industry, which uses natural resources, will provide sustainable developments for printing for the future. Natural pigments will protect nature by eliminating the damage to the environment. It will increase the use of environmentally friendly inks in the market, especially by being used in food and packaging printing (Liu et al., 2014)

Sinop clay is found in large quantities in the province of Sinop in the Black Sea region of Turkey and takes its name from this city. Sinop clay is abundant in this region. Due to its easy use and low cost, Sinop clay can be suitable for use in new and different industrial applications. Sinop clay, which was used in many fields before, was also used as an alternative pigment for lithography printing inks.

Figure 1. Sinop Clay and its pigment state.

The aim of the study is to create a pigment from Sinop clay, which is a cheap and easily accessible natural pigment. Making Lithography ink from this created pigment. Printing with the produced ink, examining the prints in terms of printability, and producing ink in order to more easily reach the Pantone color obtained as a result of the mixture of many colors.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of ink

The soil taken from the Sinop region of Turkey is ground into pigment. The prepared pigments were mixed into the varnish formulation given in Table 1 at the rates in Table 2. and turned into lithography ink. Ink 1 contains 20% and Ink 2 contains 25% pigment.

Table 1. Ingredients of varnish.

Ingredient	Varnish	Quantity
Oil	Linseed oil	50 g
Resin	Phenolic resin	35 g
°C/Time	300°C/20 min	

Table 2. Ingredients of inks.

Inks	Quantity
Ink 1	Varnish (78.5%) + Sinop pigment (20%) + Linseed oil (1.5%)
Ink 2	Varnish (73%) + Sinop pigment (25%) + Linseed oil (2%)

2.2 Printing and measuring of prepared Inks

Before test prints, glossy coated papers (Table 3) were conditioned in the print room at $23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $50\% \pm 3\%$ relative humidity for 24 hours. Test prints were carried out according to the ISO 2864-1:2017 is suitable for four-colour printing

on printability tester. Test prints were made with IGT C1 test print device under 400 N pressure. Each sample was printed on at least 5 different papers.

Table 3. Optical properties of papers used in printing.

Properties	Paper
Grammage	170 g/m ²
Thickness	151 μm
Gloss (75°)	61.3
L*	95.03
a*	0.98
b*	-3.57

Measurements of the printed samples were made with X-Rite eXact Spectrophotometer (X-Rite, Germany). The measurement conditions of the spectrophotometer were determined as polarization filter with 0/45° geometry with 2° observer angle with D50 illuminant in the range of 400-700 nm. Color measurements were made with CIE L*a*b* color system according to ISO 12647-2:2013 standard. The measured color differences were calculated with Formula (1) according to the CIE ΔE₀₀ ISO 11664-6:2014 standard. Gloss measurements of the prints were made using a micro-TRI-gloss (60° geometry) gloss meter (BYK Gardner, Germany) according to ISO 2813.

$$\Delta E_{00} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta L'}{k_L S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H}\right)^2} + R_T \frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C} \frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Rub resistance test

TMI Rub resistance tester was used to measure the abrasion on the papers on which the inks were printed. Measurements were made according to ASTM D5264-98 (2019) test standard, using metal test block weighing 920 gr weight, as 30 oscillations.

3 RESULTS

Optical properties, printability, L*a*b* values and ΔE₀₀ values of Sinop pigmented inks printed on coated paper were measured and analyzed. The measurement results are given in Tables 4 and 5. The surface images of the test prints are given in Figure 2.

Table 4. Reference Pantone® color L*a*b* values.

Reference Inks	L*	a*	b*
Pantone 7527 C	85.58	0.4	10.97
Pantone 400 C	78.06	1.03	7

Pantone Warm Gray 1C	85.16	1.47	2.11
----------------------	-------	------	------

Table 5. Measurement results of the inks L*a*b* values.

				Pantone® 7527 C	Pantone® 400 C	Pantone® Warm Gray 1C
Inks	L*	a*	b*	ΔE_{00}	ΔE_{00}	ΔE_{00}
Ink 1	85.59	1.4	8.88	2.31	7.76	6.78
Ink 2	80.52	1.58	10.33	5.23	4.17	9.43

When we look at the ΔE values obtained, it has been determined that the Ink1 values are quite close to the Pantone® 7527 C values. ΔE_{00} value was calculated as 2.31. This means that the human eye cannot differentiate between the two colors. In addition, ΔE_{00} value was below 5 when Ink 2 and Pantone® 400 C were compared. It is within acceptable values.

Figure 2. Surface images of test prints.

When the surface images of the test prints are examined, it is seen that the pigment ratio creates a color difference.

Figure 3. Comparison of Ink 1 and Pantone® 7527 C surface images.

It is also seen in the image that the surface images of Ink 1 and Pantone® 7527 C are almost indistinguishable when compared.

Table 6. Gloss values of the inks.

<i>Inks</i>	<i>Gloss 60°</i>
<i>Ink 1</i>	<i>34.12</i>
<i>Ink 2</i>	<i>27.33</i>
<i>Pantone 7527 C</i>	<i>45.43</i>
<i>Pantone 400 C</i>	<i>49.4</i>
<i>Pantone Warm Gray 1C</i>	<i>53.85</i>

When the gloss values were compared, it was determined that the closest values were ink 1 and Pantone® 7527 C.

Figure 4. Rub resistance surface images Ink 1 (left) Ink 2 (right).

Ink rub resistance refers to the degree of ink film that is scratched or peeled off by rubbing. The main factors affecting the rubbing resistance of the ink are the basic properties of the paper, the composition of the ink and the printing conditions. (Wenhua et al., 2012) When looking at the images, it has been determined that the ink rub resistance is better in Ink 1 than Ink 2. As the pigment ratio increased, the rubbing resistance decreased.

4 CONCLUSIONS

It is known that environmentally friendly products have come to the fore in recent years. The use of natural and nature-identical raw materials will also protect the future of the world. In this context, lithography ink was produced with the pigment obtained from Sinop clay, which is natural and easily obtained from the Sinop region, which is both inexpensive and very easy to process.

The CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ values of the obtained ink were measured and compared with the Pantone® catalogue. As a result of the comparison, Pantone® 7527 C color and Ink 1 were extremely similar. The calculated ΔE_{00} value is 2.31. This showed that the ink would successfully create the same color.

When the gloss values were compared, it was determined that especially ink 1 was close to the gloss values of Pantone 7527 C ink.

When the rub resistance was examined, it was determined that the increase in the pigment ratio in the ink decreased the rub resistance value of the ink.

5 REFERENCES

- Abdelmaksoud, W.M. (2022). Synthesis of eco-friendly cobalt doped willemite blue pigment from white sand for multi-applications in coatings and inks. *Pigment Resin Technol.*
- Aydemir, C., & Yenidoğan, S. (2018). Light fastness of printing inks: A review. *Journal of Graphic Engineering & Design (JGED)*, 9(1).
- Erhan, S. Z., & Bagby, M. O. (1995). Vegetable-oil-based printing ink formulation and degradation. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 3(4), 237-246.
- Hayta, P., Oktav, M., & Ateş Duru, Ö. (2022). Evaluation of plant-based oils for production of offset printing ink. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 99(8), 711-719.
- Liu, G., Chen, Q., & Chen, G. (2018). Extraction of natural pigment from purple potato in preparation of edible ink. In *Applied Sciences in Graphic*

Communication and Packaging: Proceedings of 2017 49th Conference of the International Circle of Educational Institutes for Graphic Arts Technology and Management & 8th China Academic Conference on Printing and Packaging (pp. 717-721). Springer Singapore.

Liu, Z., Liu, Q., Yang, L., Sun, J. Y., Ma, G. Y., & Zhang, B. L. (2014). Preparation and study on temperature-resistance environment-friendly ink based on natural pigment and soybean oil. *Appl. Mech. Mater.*, 469, 13-16.

Özcan, A. (2007). Kağıt-mürekkep seçim Kriterlerinin basılabilirlik açısından saptanması (Doctoral dissertation, Marmara Üniversitesi (Turkey)).

Ozcan, A., & Tutak, D. (2021). The effect of paper surface-coating pigments and binders on colour gamut and printing parameters. *Coloration Technology*, 137(5), 445-455.

Sabin, P., Benjelloun-Mlayah, B., & Delmas, M. (1997). Offset printing inks based on rapeseed oil and sunflower oil. Part II: Varnish and ink formulation. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 74(10), 1227-1233.

Wenhua Z, Beihai H, Chunxiu Z, Yue H. Analysis on ink layer rub resistance for coated paper prints. *Adv. Mater. Res.*, 2012; 380: 173 -8.